

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF PERSONS LIVING WITH HIV/AIDS ACCESSING CARE IN KOGI STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Kogi State is one of the high risk States in Nigeria for HIV/AIDS with a prevalence of 5.5% in the general population. Attributes of persons living with HIV/AIDS in the State have not been documented. This study was designed to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of persons living with HIV infection accessing health care in the State. **Methods:** Descriptive cross-sectional study design was used. Patients enrolled in the study were drawn from five health care facilities where antiretroviral clinics were located in the State. A total of 252 persons living with HIV/AIDS who were consecutively present over a period of one month in each facility were interviewed using a structured questionnaire. **Results:** Mean age of respondents was 34.8±1.2 years, with the highest proportion of 21.4% in ages 20 – 24 years. Majority (62.7%) were females, while 51.6% indicated that they were currently married, while 22.3% reported having more than one spouse. The Ebira (25.8%) and Igala (25.8%) ethnic groups accounted for the majority of respondents. In terms of religious affiliation, 53.2% indicated being Christians while 45.2% were Muslims. Educational status showed that 67.5% had education up to the secondary school level. Traders (39.7%) accounted for the majority in terms of occupational background. **Conclusion:** Persons living with HIV/AIDS accessing health care in the State were young adults and most of them women.

KEYWORDS: HIV/AIDS, PLWHA, Socio-demographic profile, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS), a pandemic disease condition, has claimed the lives of many and affected the growth and development of many countries with sub-Saharan Africa being the worst hit region. In 2008, Sub-Saharan Africa accounted for 67% of HIV infections worldwide (UNAIDS/WHO, 2009). According to the epidemiological report on HIV/AIDS, an estimated 33.2 million persons worldwide were living with HIV at the end of 2007, 2.7 million became newly infected with HIV, and 2.1 million people lost their lives to AIDS (Uwimana and Struthers, 2007; UNAIDS/WHO, 2007).

Globally, the greatest mortality is found among people between the ages of 20 and 40 years which have dramatically changed the life expectancy in most affected parts of the world (Parks, 2009). In Nigeria, HIV/AIDS epidemic has continued to be a serious problem ever since it was first reported in the country in 1986 (Nasidi and Harry, 2006). Nigeria's HIV/AIDS epidemic is characterised by one of the most rapidly increasing rates of new cases in West Africa and as a result, the crude death rate was about 20% in 2000 than in 1990 (Sentinel survey, 2005).

Statistics revealed that Nigeria's national average of HIV prevalence at present is 4.6% with an estimated 3.1% of adults between ages 15 – 49 living with the disease condition (NACA, 2009; UNAIDS, 2008). This infection rate, although lower than that of other African countries such as South Africa and Zambia, should be considered in the context of Nigeria's relatively large population of approximately 140 million of which over 3 million people are still living with HIV while 1 million children are still orphaned by the disease (Ogunde, 2008; ENHANSE, 2003; Sentinel survey, 2005). HIV prevalence at regional as well as state level, also show marked variation with a prevalence ranged from a low of 1.0% in the Southwest (Ekiti State) to a high of 10.6% in the North central parts (Benue State) (NACA, 2009).

Death due to AIDS has resulted to a significant decline in Nigeria's life expectancy. In 1991 the average life expectancy was 53.8 years for women and 52.6 years for men. In 2007 these figures had fallen to 46 for women and 47 for men (UNAIDS, 2008; WHO, 2008).

Certain factors such as low literacy level, high rates of casual and transactional unprotected sex, particularly among youths aged 15 – 24, poverty as well as cultural and religious factors have been identified as major factors in the transmission of HIV in Nigeria (NACA, 2009).

The culture of marrying at early age is now being practiced in almost all parts of the nation, particularly among the female population. This has brought about a low literacy level among the female gender and an increased vulnerability to infectious sexual diseases (Olanikeet *al.*, 2007). Glynn *et al* (2008) reported that in some African countries, married 15 – 19 years old females have higher levels of HIV infection compared to non-married sexually active females of the same age.

Traditionally, Nigerian women marry at a young age. However the average age of marriage varies from state to state. A 2007 study revealed that 54% of girls from the North West between ages 15 – 24 were married by age 15 and 81% were married by age 18. The study showed that the younger married girls lacked knowledge on reproductive health including HIV and AIDS (The Population Council, 2007). This practice can contribute to the spread of HIV because the men who are considerably older are likely to have been involved in multiple sex and other high risk sexual behaviours (NDHS, 2008; Olanikeet *al.*, 2007).

Findings have shown a dwindling polygynous family system in Nigeria. Among the Yorubas, there is evidence of decrease in the number of polygynous marriages (Tinuola, 2003). However, the struggle to have as many children as possible in a family encourages the culture of marrying more than one wife by most men in Nigeria, which results in high susceptibility to Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs) including HIV/AIDS infection among females (Olanikeet *al.*, 2007). Osagbemi *et al.*, (1999) also found that multiple sexual partnering, particularly among individuals who participate in spouse sharing is a significant risk factor in the spread of STIs. Polygyny and cultural heterosexual relationships, have implications for the frequency of sexual intercourse, and thus, may affect fertility and impact on HIV/AIDS control (NDHS, 2008; Jegede, 2005).

Several studies have also linked poverty to the spread of HIV/AIDS virus in both developed and developing countries (Bamett and Whiteside, 2002; Lazzarini, 2002; Bureau of Global Health, 2003; Catholic Agency for Overseas Development, 2003). Lazzarini (2002) pointed out that in the period from 1998 through 1999 rates of death from AIDS were consistently associated with poverty. The lower the income for the country, the higher the rate of death.

Kogi State is one of the States in the North central Nigeria, with a high prevalence of HIV. The prevalence of 5.5% reported in the State is higher than the overall national prevalence of 4.6% (NACA, 2007; NACA, 2009). The attributes of the persons living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) in the State have not been documented. This study was therefore, designed to describe the socio-demographic characteristics of PLWHA attending antiretroviral therapy clinics in five healthcare facilities in Kogi State, Nigeria.

METHODS

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used. All the five health care facilities in Kogi State where antiretroviral clinics are located and accessed by PLWHA were visited. These facilities include; Federal Medical Centre Lokoja (47), Partners against AIDS in the Community (PAAC) Obangede (60), St John's Catholic Hospital Kabba (56), Grimard Hospital Anyigba (55) and the Evangelical Church of West Africa (ECWA) Hospital Ebge (36). All persons with sero-positive HIV status who presented consecutively during a month of a visit to each facility were included.

Data was obtained using a structured questionnaire administered at the time of an interview. The data obtained included the age, sex, and other social and demographic characteristics. Ethical clearance was obtained from the hospitals used. Informed written consent was taken from the participants, and confidentiality of information was assured.

Data entry and statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software, version 14.0. Data was summarized using proportions.

RESULTS

A total of 252 PLWHA were interviewed with the highest proportion of 24% from Partners against AIDS in the Community (PAAC) Obangede. Mean age of respondents was 34.8 ± 1.2 years, with the highest proportion of 21.4% in ages 20 -24 years. Majority (62.7%) were females, while 51.6% indicated that they were currently in a marital relationship. Of those who were married, 22.3% reported having two spouses. The Ebira (25.8%) and Igala (25.8%) ethnic groups accounted for the majority of respondents while 45.2% were Muslims. Educational Status showed that 67.5% had education up to the secondary school level. Traders (39.7%) accounted for the majority in terms of occupational background (Tables 1 – 4).

Table 1: Socio-demographic status of participants

Variables	Categories	N	%
Gender (n = 252)	Male	96	37.3
	Female	158	62.7
Tribe (n = 252)	Yoruba	60	23.8
	Ebira	65	25.8
	Igala	65	25.8
	Bassa	13	5.2
Marital Status (n= 252)	Married	130	51.6
	Single	60	23.8
	Widowed	26	10.3
	Divorced	16	6.3
	Separated	12	4.8
	Co-habitation	8	3.2
Educational status (n = 252)	Primary	72	28.6
	Secondary	98	38.9
	Tertiary	38	15.1
	No education	44	17.5
Religion (n = 252)	Christians	134	53.2
	Muslims	114	45.2
	Others	4	1.6

Table 2: Age distribution of participants

Age group (years)	N	%
<15	None	-
15 – 19	43	17.1
20 – 24	54	21.4
25 – 29	41	16.3
30 – 34	37	14.7
35 – 39	19	7.5
40 – 44	23	9.1
45 – 49	16	6.3
50 – 55	11	4.4
>55	8	3.2
Total	252	100.0

Mean age: 34.8 ± 1.2 years

Table 3: Number of spouse among the married population

Number of spouse	No. of Males	%	No. of Females	%	Total	%
1	20	43.5	81	96.4	101	77.7
2	23	50.0	3	3.6	26	20.0
3 and above	3	6.5	None	-	3	2.3
Total	46	100.0	84	100.0	130	100.0

Table 4: Occupational engagement among participants

Occupation (n = 252)	N	%
Civil servants	40	15.9
Traders	100	39.7
Farmers	14	5.5
Students	34	13.5
Others	64	25.4

DISCUSSION

In this study, females were 62.7% of the PLWHA interviewed. This finding conforms with that of Adedimeji and Odutolu (2007) in their study on care, support and quality of life outcomes among PLWHA accessing HAART in Southwest Nigeria and the reports of Alemayhu *et al.* (2008) on predictors of adherence to antiretroviral therapy among HIV infected persons in the southwest of Ethiopia. Uwimana and Struthers' (2007) study on met and unmet palliative care needs of people living with HIV/AIDS in Rwanda indicated that 176 (71%) of the 250 participants were females which, further supports the findings in the present study. According to the United Nations (UN) report (2001), HIV infection rate among females has steadily increased exceeding the rates in males. The UN highlighted that the increase was attributable to the vulnerabilities of women and girls in addition to social norms that deny women sexual health knowledge and practices to control their body (sexual negotiation) which, enhances their vulnerability. Women's vulnerability to HIV in Sub – Saharan Africa also stems from legal and economic disadvantages they often confront. A comprehensive epidemiological review undertaken in connection with the modes of transmission study in Lesotho found that sexual and physical violence is a key determinant of the country's severe HIV epidemic. According to a recent survey, 47% of men and 40% of women in Lesotho say women have no right to refuse sex with their husbands or boyfriends (UNAIDS/WHO, 2009).

Although HIV/AIDS affects all age groups, those in the reproductive age seem to be most vulnerable. Reports have revealed that in Kenya, women between 20 and 24 years are 5.5 times more likely to be living with HIV than their male counterparts while among people aged 15 - 24 in the United Republic of Tanzania, females are four times more likely than males to be living with HIV (UNAIDS/WHO, 2009). In the present study, the respondents were within the age range of 18 to 58 years with the majority (21.4%) observed to be within 20 – 24 years. The mean age of 35 years found in this study is similar to the findings of Alamayehu *et al.* (2008) and Adedimeji and Odutolu (2007).

The present study revealed that 51.6% of participants were married. This is seen to be quite different from other findings (Alemayhu *et al.*, 2008; Adedimeji and Odutolu, 2007; Odimayo *et al.*, 2010), in which the proportion of married respondents were lower. These observed differences could be attributed to traditional practice of polygamy, spouse sharing and early marriage in some areas of Kogi State, which are perceived as reasons that perpetuate HIV/AIDS infection in marriage. This study indicated that 22.3% of the 130 married respondents have two or more spouses with the majority being male (56.5%). Studies have shown a close association between the incidence of STIs, including HIV, and simultaneous keeping of multiple sex partners (Reiss and Leik, 1989; Olaleye, 2003; Jegede, 2005).

The Okun people of Kogi State have been linked with a practice involving the acceptance of sexual relation between men and wives of their kin. This is known as spouse-sharing which is viewed as an important way of life. A study conducted by Osagbemi *et al.* (1999) on spouse-sharing and experiences with sexually transmitted diseases among the Okuns showed that 65.3% reported practicing spouse-sharing and about 22% of the sampled respondents reported STI experience an indication of the health risk of spouse-sharing.

Data from this study revealed a decreasing trend of HIV prevalence as respondents' level of education increases. For instance majority of the respondents were individuals who had education up to secondary school (67.5%), whereas only 15.1% had education up to tertiary level. Low understanding of the knowledge acquired by respondents with lower educational attainment on HIV/AIDS and their willingness and ability to utilize such information in taking informed decision relating to HIV/AIDS preventions may have contributed to their increased prevalence (Odimayo *et al.*, 2010).

Assessing respondents' occupational risk in acquiring HIV, this study indicated that traders suffered the highest prevalence with 39.7%. This observation may be due to the fact that some traders travel long distances away

from their spouses spending many days before they return and as such may involve in illicit unprotected sex that may lead to STIs including HIV.

In conclusion, this study provides information on the characteristics of PLWHA accessing treatment in five healthcare facilities within Kogi state, Nigeria. These findings has socio – economic implication and agree with those reported in other parts of the world particularly in Africa that young adults of reproductive age (20 – 24) are at higher risk for the disease and that the prevalence of HIV among females is higher when compared with their male counterparts.

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